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CURRENT STATUS OF THE PROCESS OF CATALYTIC REFORMING OF GASOLINES

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Annotation. In the course of the study, the component composition of the products of separation of raw materials, catalytic reforming and isomerization was determined; analysis of the influence of the composition of raw materials on the quality of gasoline; recommendations for adjusting the technological regime of the raw material separation unit are proposed; with the help of mathematical modeling methods, the properties of commercial gasolines were studied and the optimal flow ratios for blending gasoline formulations based on the studied raw materials were selected.

The results of the study will help improve the resource efficiency of the gasoline production process at the enterprise and ensure that the product complies with all the standards and requirements contained in the regulatory documentation.

In different countries, produced motor gasolines differ significantly from each other in composition. This can be explained by differences not only in national

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standards, but also by the ratio of refinery capacities for the production of various gasoline components.

Despite the tightening of environmental requirements for produced gasoline, the catalytic reforming process is still one of the leading ones in modern oil refining. Restrictions on the content of aromatic compounds lead to a decrease in the proportion of reformate, but, despite this, the growth of the capacity of this process continues due to an increase in the total world consumption of gasoline.

In the process of catalytic reforming, chemical reactions occur, as a result of which low-octane straight-run gasolines and heavy naphtha coming from the oil distillation unit are converted into reformate containing high-octane compounds, among which there is benzene.

The main reactions of the reforming process are [1]:

- dehydrogenation of naphthenes with the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons;
- dehydrocyclization of paraffins into aromatic compounds;
- isomerization of paraffins and naphthenes;
- dehydrogenation of paraffins to olefins;
- hydrocracking of paraffins.

The first three reactions are targeted, due to the formation of aromatics, they increase the octane numbers of the components for the further production of motor gasoline. Dehydrogenation and hydrocracking should be minimized because they are side reactions.

Favorable conditions for the occurrence of target reactions are the presence of low pressures and high temperatures.

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Dehydrogenation and dehydrocyclization reactions are endothermic, requiring constant heating of the incoming stream after each reactor by continuously passing it through the furnace section. All reactions except hydrocracking produce hydrogen, which can be used in hydrotreating and hydrocracking processes.

Commercial schemes typically consist of a series of three to six fixed or moving bed reactors. The feedstock sent to the catalytic reforming process is first hydrotreated to remove sulfur, nitrogen and metals.

In a continuous reforming process, the catalyst can be regenerated in one of the reactors and typically once to twice a day without production downtime. In semi-regenerative systems, regeneration of all reactors with catalysts is carried out simultaneously after several months (sometimes even after a year). The tightening of standards for the content of benzene in motor gasolines limits the use of this process to increase the octane numbers of oil refining products.

However, the catalytic reforming process still serves to obtain one of the basic high-octane components of the production of motor gasoline, both in Russia and abroad. It is catalytic reforming gasolines in the largest quantities (56.2% by volume) that are included in the composition of motor gasolines produced at refineries in the Russian Federation.

And the shares, for example, isomerizate and alkylate are only 1.5% vol. and 0.3% vol. respectively [2]. And it is much lower than in Western countries.

Currently, every year, both at Russian and foreign refineries, there is a constant modernization of the reforming process units. It is based on tightening the technological regime, for example, on reducing pressure in order to obtain high-

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octane components of gasoline, the octane number of which reaches approximately 98-100 units. To reduce the pressure in the plants, it is necessary to introduce highly stable catalysts into the process and install an additional reactor to increase the catalyst load, which carries out the dualforming process - continuous catalyst regeneration. This allows to increase the service life of the catalyst, and also reduces the rigidity of the process in the head reactors.

Thus, modern reforming processes in Russia are being improved every day due to the modernization of existing plants, but with the priority use of new domestic catalysts, or through the development of new catalysts and the type of reactor devices, the stability of their operation, as well as an increase in the depth of processing of raw materials. Improvement in the technology of the reforming process made it possible to reduce the operating pressure by more than ten times.

For the catalytic reforming process, as well as for the isomerization process, bifunctional catalysts should be used when both components, metal and oxide, play an active role. They are platinum crystals deposited on aluminum oxide. The platinum must be dispersed over the alumina surface so that the maximum amount of active metal sites is available for dehydrogenation.

The hydrogenation/dehydrogenation, dehydrocyclization and hydrogenolysis reactions are catalyzed by the metal sites of the catalyst. Isomerization, hydrocracking and sometimes dehydrocyclization proceed on the oxide component. To reduce the activity of platinum, it is used sulfiding, in order to reduce the bulk of the hydrogenolysis or metal-catalyzed cracking reactions. As a result of the poisoning of platinum, the yield of liquid products is increased, and

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the production of light gases, in particular methane, is reduced.

The interregeneration period of catalysts in a fixed bed reactor is more than a year. To increase the service life and reduce the effect of coke accumulation, modifiers are added to the catalysts - rhenium and, to a lesser extent, iridium.

In moving bed plants, the catalyst flows through the reactors and is continuously regenerated in a separate regenerator that is part of the reactor-regenerator loop. Process conditions are much more severe, shortening catalyst life and requiring several days of regeneration. Elements such as tin and germanium are added to the moving bed catalyst to increase the yield of liquid products, aromatics and hydrogen by reducing the activity of platinum [2]. These components also provide some stabilization of the catalyst with respect to platinum only.

One of the main performance characteristics of catalysts is activity, which corresponds to the depth of conversion of the feedstock. The content of aromatic compounds is an indicator of activity.

The following performance characteristic is responsible for the yield of hydrogen and liquid target products - the selectivity of the catalyst. It maximizes the desired reactions, namely aromatization, and minimizes the activity of the catalyst in side reactions, such as hydrogenolysis, which leads to the formation of gaseous hydrocarbons.

Preservation of the initial activity and selectivity over time provides the third characteristic - the stability of the catalyst. It is responsible for a long service life and an inter-regeneration period.

Another important characteristic of a catalyst is its mechanical strength. The higher

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its value, the more resistant the catalyst to crushing and abrasion.

Domestic catalysts, for example, the AP series, consist of platinum distributed over the entire volume of alumina promoted by fluorine or chlorine. Some of the catalysts in this series are sulphurized during manufacture in order to suppress the side reactions of hydrogenolysis.

In more modern catalysts of the KR series, together with platinum, a metal promoter, rhenium, is used. Its introduction provides increased stability and reduces the content of platinum, allows you to reduce the operating pressure on the reformer unit and increase the reformat yield. But a significant disadvantage of the use of polymetallic catalysts is the need for a deeper purification of raw materials from impurities.

At present, in reforming process technologies on domestic catalysts, along with the AP and KR series, catalysts of the RB series are used. For example, the firm "OLKAT" has developed a new polymetallic spherical catalyst RB-44U grade Sh [3]. This catalyst is designed for fixed bed installations. Its granules have a perfect spherical shape, and the carrier is made from high-purity aluminum hydroxide powder. The high-quality ball catalyst RB-44U provides a reformat yield of 88.9 wt. % with an octane number of 96-98 units (according to IM) and has a wide range of advantages: complete absence of dust formation, high strength, uniform layer density, ease of use, does not require special equipment for layer compaction during loading, is not compacted during operation, has high rates of activity and selectivity.

SPF "OLKAT" is engaged in the constant development and improvement of

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catalysts, the search for new solutions for their optimization. At present, a special catalyst of the brand SG-3P-M has been developed for the production of motor gasoline components, which provides a high reformat yield of 92 wt. % with an octane number of 95–96 units according to IM [4]. This catalyst surpasses the results of all platinum-rhenium compositions in terms of industrial operation. It has a high activity - it works at low process temperatures, as well as a high space velocity, i.e. of this catalyst, the quantity required is two times less than that of the traditional one.

Another high-quality polymetallic alumina-platinum catalyst RB-55D is designed for the production of high-octane components of motor gasoline with an octane rating of 100 according to IM. It is applied to continuous regeneration plants, provides high performance and high reformat yield, low platinum loss and low abrasion, as well as high thermal stability and long service life.

Generations of catalysts continue to change, but platinum has always been an indispensable component. UOP uses the most advanced technologies to achieve various goals. They offer equipment for cyclic, stationary and continuous reforming.

In the spirit of continuous innovation, UOP has introduced two new catalysts [4]. The latest R-560 fixed bed catalyst is an optimized high performance catalyst that provides good performance and maximum process flexibility. It has the highest activity, stability and cycle time and can increase reformat yield. Another innovative catalyst, R-334, delivers even higher product yields, as well as hydrogen and aromatics yields, resulting in increased profitability.

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Another foreign company, Axens, also improves old and develops new catalysts to optimize the process, for example, catalysts of the RG-582 type. RG-682. PR-9 and PR-15 [5].

Catalysts of the RC series for the process of continuous regeneration reforming were developed by NPP Neftekhim LLC [6]. The performance characteristics of this series of catalysts are very competitive compared to other catalysts from world famous catalyst manufacturers.

Catalyst RC-12 is a high activity platinum-tin catalyst for moving bed units, designed to produce reformat with maximum yield and octane, also in heavy duty applications it has low coking, high mechanical strength and density, long service life.

Another advantage of these catalysts is their compatibility. RC series catalysts are used for both full and partial replacement during operation, as they are compatible with the catalysts used in most operating reformers.

Currently, two main brands of catalysts have been developed, which differ in physical and chemical properties:

RC-12 and RC-120. They are a modified alumina-platinum spherical moving bed reforming catalyst. These catalysts have been successfully tested and recommended for use in existing plants. The choice of a specific brand of catalyst depends on the operating conditions in the installation and the need for complete or partial replacement of the existing catalyst.

Also, NPP Neftekhim LLC developed reforming catalysts of the REF series for fixed-bed semi-regenerative plants. REF-21, REF-23, and REF-24 catalysts have a

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good reputation at Russian refineries [7].

Today NPP Neftekhim LLC presents a new line of products in this series - catalysts REF-125 and REF-130, also a modified aluminum-platinum catalyst only for fixed bed reforming, which are characterized by higher stability. The new catalysts are based on a common technology with the introduction of a stabilizing complex. REF-125 and REF-130 provide high performance in terms of activity, selectivity, maintenance cycle and overall life. Between themselves, these two brands differ in the ratio of platinum and rhenium.

reformer licensors UOP and Axens are also playing a major role in the development of platinum -tin pellet catalysts for continuous regeneration reformers. UOP introduced as many as five new series of these catalysts [8].

The advantages of the R-160 catalyst are a lower amount of platinum and an increase in bulk density. The R-170 catalyst is characterized by increased reformat yield. R-230 has the least coke formation and maximum thermal stability.

Axens has released a new series of spherical catalysts CR-700 to produce a reformat for motor gasolines and AR-500 for refining to produce aromatic compounds [9].

The presented new catalysts are characterized by a high yield of aromatic compounds, as well as increased thermal stability and specific surface area.

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